

Report on models for extreme winds Deliverable D4.2

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Executive Summary

This report describes the procedures that were proposed to derive extreme wind estimates for the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA). Data basis for the estimations are the NEWA mesoscale simulations comprising the NEWA mesoscale wind atlas. A modified Spectral Correction Method (SCM) is applied to take the smoothing effect of these data in comparison to on-site measurements into account. Initial verifications show that this correction approach works quite well for simple offshore sites without significant microscale effects. For more complex sites an additional downscaling approach is required, that is described in this report but could not be applied anymore due to missing input data which are required from the processed wind atlas data.

1. Introduction

The European scale project New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) aims at developing a New European Wind Atlas as a new standard for site assessment in wind energy. The atlas is being developed on the basis of mesoscale simulations using the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF). The simulations will be supported and validated by a large number of field measurements stemming from various met masts and measurement campaigns across Europe, see e.g. [1]. One considered specific feature of the atlas will be the estimation of extreme winds, which play a decisive role for the design of wind turbines and wind farms. In order to make sure that the wind does not exceed a wind turbine's design specification, reliable estimates of extreme winds are crucial. Following the IEC-61400-1:2005 standard [2], we are interested in the 10-min-average wind speed at hub height, which has a recurrence period of 50 years. This wind is often referred to as the 50-year wind.

This report focuses on the development and validation of the extreme wind estimation procedure applied to the NEWA simulations. Our study – based on which this estimation procedure was tested and refined – makes use of a set of 10 years of simulations covering central Europe, which were performed in the context of the beta production runs in Task 4.3 (cf. NEWA deliverable D4.3). The resulting extreme wind estimates will be compared to estimates from measurements at various sites of different complexity. This validation is the basis for the definition of the estimation procedure to be applied to the final production runs of NEWA and thus for the final extreme wind estimates that will be offered in the wind atlas database.

Estimating the 50-year wind for a site based on mesoscale simulations is a very challenging task. Firstly, smoothing is embedded in the mesoscale simulations in order to ensure numerical stability leading to an effective resolution several times coarser than the spatial resolution setup. This smoothing effect leads to a reduced variability of the wind and consequently to an underestimation of extreme winds. Thus in one main part of this report, we focus on correcting this smoothing effect in the mesoscale modeled winds using the spectral correction method (SCM) [3, 4, 5]. For this purpose, resulting extreme wind estimates at offshore sites and a simple onshore site are compared to measurements. We expect the small-scale effects, described in the following paragraph, to be negligible offshore allowing an isolated investigation of the smoothing effect. Secondly, the mesoscale models describe the orography and surface roughness around the site on relatively coarse grids. Thus, for example, local, small-scale speed-up effects through hills or surface roughness changes may not be captured. Thus, in a second main part of this report, we investigate the combination of the SCM with a downscaling approach, in order to take the small-scale orography and roughness into account. After generalizing the data to a flat terrain with a uniform roughness of $z_0 = 0.05$ m following e.g. [6], the SCM is applied to the resulting generalized time series. Afterwards, the corrected generalized wind climate can be used as an input to WAsP Engineering to calculate the site-specific extreme winds. The resulting extreme estimates are compared with measurements from several sites of different complexity.

The report is structured as follows. In Section 2.1, the mesoscale simulations used for our study are introduced followed by the measurement data which are used for validation in Section 2.2. Section 3 consists of a first validation study offshore to investigate the application of the SCM to the NEWA simulations. Subsequently, in Section 4, we discuss one specific aspect of the obtained results (Section 3), namely the inter-annual variability of the annual maxima, in greater detail. In Section 6, the combination of the SCM with a downscaling approach is presented. In Section 7, we summarize our findings and recommend a final procedure for the extreme wind estimation and presentation in the final wind atlas database.

2. Data sources used for testing and validating the procedure

2.1 Mesoscale model simulations with WRF

The mesoscale wind atlas, as part of the NEWA project, is simulated with the widely used open-source mesoscale model WRF [7] version 3.8.1. For our validation study, we used the data from the preliminary NEWA simulations, which were performed in the context of the beta production runs in Task 4.3. The data cover a period of ten years (2008-2017) from one sub-domain of the wind atlas covering Central Europe.

The horizontal resolution of the innermost model domain is 3 km. The wind atlas consists of week-long simulations, driven by the ERA5 climate reanalysis dataset and using the MYNN PBL scheme [8, 9]. The output contains a number of atmospheric variables at several heights from 10 m to 500 m with an output time step of 30 min corresponding to an output frequency of 48 day⁻¹. A snapshot of the simulations showing the instantaneous wind speed at 100 m height is shown in Figure 1 for one selected point in time.

Figure 1: Simulation snapshot of the WRF model domain for central Europe. The color denotes the wind speed in ms^{-1} at a height of 100 m. The black dots represent the approximate positions of the first selected measurement sites.

2.2 Measurements used for validations

In order to validate our estimations of extreme winds, in the first validation phase time series of wind speed from four different measurement sites are used, and for the second phase six further sites, which are all briefly listed in Table 1. Locations of the sites from the first phase are shown in Figure 1: FINO1 and FINO3 are located in the North Sea, FINO2 in the Baltic Sea and the met mast Cabauw onshore Western of the Netherlands.

All measurements are performed by cup anemometers and the considered data consists of ten-min-average wind speeds given every ten minutes. Measurement gaps smaller than six hours have been linearly interpolated. Longer gaps were omitted for the calculation of the spectra. We have only used time series which overlap with the completed simulations even though longer measurement time series are partially available.

Site	Height [m]	Period [years]	Terrain
FINO1	100	10	offshore
FINO2	102	9	offshore
FINO3	90	8	offshore
Cabauw	80	10	flat
Ijmuiden	85	4	offshore
Lindenberg	98	9	forest, one hill
Hovsore	80	13	coastal
Hamburg	110	14	urban, flat
Karlsruhe	100	9	rather flat, forested
Tystofte	39	..	coastal

Table 1: Description of measurement sites used for validation.

3. Estimation of extreme winds for offshore sites: investigation of the smoothing effect

The major part of of this section has been published as:

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3.1 Introduction

As discussed in Section 1, the smoothing effect of the mesoscale simulations leads to a reduced variability of the wind speeds and consequently to an underestimation of extreme winds. This section focuses on correcting the smoothing effect in the mesoscale modeled winds using the spectral correction method (SCM) [3, 4, 5]. The SCM has shown some promising results in connection with the use of reanalysis data [4]. However, its performance is expected to vary with different model outputs and the

simulations from NEWA are of a much finer resolution (3 km) than the modeled data that have been previously used in connection with the SCM (about 50 km). Hence, the major goal of this section is to examine the performance of the SCM in combination with the simulations used for the New European Wind Atlas.

For this purpose, we will apply the spectral correction method (SCM) to the data from the NEWA simulations (Section 2.1) at the three offshore locations Fino1, FINO2 and FINO3 and the simple onshore site Cabauw and compare the resulting estimates to the estimates from the measurements (Section 2.2). We expect the local effects of orography and surface roughness to be negligible for the offshore sites and partially also for the simple onshore case. This is expected to allow an isolated investigation of the smoothing effect.

3.2 Methodology

Extreme Wind Estimation

We define $u_{max}^{(i)}$ as the annual maximum of the i -th year, while $\langle u_{max} \rangle = \langle u_{max}^{(i)} \rangle_i$ denotes the average annual maximum, which we estimate by the sample mean of the annual maxima. Following e.g. [10, 11], we assume that the annual maxima are Gumbel-distributed. We estimate the corresponding parameters α and β with the annual maximum method (AMM) [12], which is based on a probability weighted moment procedure. The estimated parameters can be used to estimate the T -year wind u_T , which is defined as the wind occurring with a probability of $\frac{1}{T}$ in one year. It is estimated by $u_T = \beta - \alpha \ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{T}{T-1} \right) \right] \approx \beta + \alpha \ln T$ (for $T \gg 1$).

The statistical uncertainties, which can be found e.g. in [5, 12], increases with T and is quite high for $T = 50$ years for only 10 years of measurements and simulations. Hence, before the 30-year simulation is ready at the end of NEWA project, we investigate not only the desired 50-year wind but also the average annual maximum, in order to compare quantities with less uncertainty and obtain a more significant validation. Additionally, in the context of the SCM we will also consider the wind $\tilde{u}_{T=1}$ with a recurrence period of $T = 1$ years, representing the wind which is exceeded once a year on average. Note that \tilde{u}_T approximately equals u_T only for $T \gg 1$, since \tilde{u}_T is not based on the annual maxima but on the complete time series.

Spectral correction method

As already mentioned in the introduction, mesoscale simulations underestimate the extreme winds due to a smoothing of the field variables such as the velocity field. When presented in the spectral domain, the spectral energy level in the mesoscale range is underestimated as can be seen by the comparison with field measurements in Figure 3 for frequencies higher than 1 day^{-1} . It has been shown, for example by Larsén et al. [13] that the power spectral density (PSD), also simply called spectrum in the following, usually follows $S(f) \propto f^{-5/3}$ above a certain frequency f_c . The frequency f_c is related to the integral time scale, which is often found to be in the order of 1 day in the mid-latitude here. Setting $S(f) \propto f^{-5/3}$ for $f > f_c = 1.5 \text{ day}^{-1}$ yields a "corrected", hybrid PSD S_{cor} , which is shown as the red dashed line in Figure 3. Note also that the corrected spectrum is extrapolated up to the output frequency of the 10-min-measurements. Choosing the value of f_c is a crucial step in the SCM and can lead to some uncertainty, as will be discussed further in Section 3.3. In order to reduce the sensitivity to f_c , the

exact value of $S_{cor}(f_c)$ is determined by a linear regression (in the log-log framework) for $1.3 \text{ day}^{-1} < f < 1.7 \text{ day}^{-1}$. For spectral peaks exceeding the used extrapolation procedure the original value of the WRF spectrum is kept.

The main idea of the SCM is to estimate a correction factor for the extreme winds based on the original and corrected spectrum following Larsén et al. [3, 4]. Under certain mathematical assumptions, such as stationarity and Gaussian-distributed u and $\dot{u} = \frac{du}{dt}$, extreme winds can be expressed based on the PSD or more precisely the spectral moments. We can even find an explicit formula for the wind \tilde{u}_{T_0} with a recurrence period of $T_0 = 1$ year. Following [3], it is given by

$$\tilde{u}_{T_0} = \langle u \rangle + \sqrt{m_0} \sqrt{2 \ln \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{m_2}{m_0}} T_0 \right)},$$

where $\langle u \rangle$ is the mean velocity and

$$m_j := 2 \int_0^\infty d\omega \omega^j S(\omega)$$

are the spectral moments. For discrete signals, we have to estimate m_2 by integrating up to only half the sampling frequency of the corresponding signal.

Due to these assumptions made, we expect high uncertainties when using the equation to estimate \tilde{u}_T . However, it has been shown that the ratio of the corrected and uncorrected values of \tilde{u}_{T_0} can lead to a good description of the smoothing effect and hence a possible correction factor. More precisely, we can estimate the spectral moments for the corrected PSD ($m_j^{(corr)}$) and uncorrected PSD (m_j) and define a correction factor

$$C := \frac{\tilde{u}_{T_0}(m_0^{(corr)}, m_2^{(corr)})}{\tilde{u}_{T_0}(m_0, m_2)}.$$

We apply the resulting factor for $T_0 = 1$ year to the extreme wind estimates directly obtained from the original simulations through the AMM. Hence, the SCM-corrected values $\langle u_{max} \rangle$ and u_T are $C \cdot \langle u_{max} \rangle$ and $C \cdot u_T$, respectively, where u_T has been estimated applying the AMM method to the original WRF simulations (see Section A). Note that in some articles C is also called smoothing effect denoted as SE.

It should be noted again that the SCM method is based on many assumptions and not all of them are fulfilled. Thus, its performance has to be assessed by the validation with measurements. Numerically, we can also estimate \tilde{u}_T or even u_T for different assumptions such as a non-Gaussian probability density function (pdf) of u .

Figure 2: Exemplary wind speed time series at the location of FINO1.

Figure 3: PSD of measurements (blue) and simulations (grey) and filtered simulations (black). The red dashed line shows the corrected PSD based on the filtered spectrum.

3.3 Results and discussion

Properties of the WRF time series

Comparing the simulated time series (grey line in Figure 2) with the measured one (blue line), we can clearly see the smoothing effect of the simulations. The measured time series contains a lot more high-frequency dynamics. Consequently, the highest wind speed in the presented time period seems to be around 5 ms^{-1} lower for the simulated time series. The missing fluctuations also manifest themselves in the lower spectral energy level of the WRF simulations for frequencies higher than approximately 1 day^{-1} , as shown in Figure 3.

At the high-frequency end of the original WRF-PSD an upward bend can be observed indicating the presence of high-frequency dynamics on scales even finer than the output frequency of 48 day^{-1} . Since we do not see this behavior in the measurements, such a bend indicates non-physical dynamics at the corresponding short time scales, as pointed out by [14] (see e.g. Figure 10). The observed high-frequency fluctuations can be artificial and numerical noises as a consequence of the high spatial resolution. Thus, a higher resolution does not necessarily lead to a more accurate simulation on small scales. In our case, however, the upward bend is weak enough so that no energy is aliased to the low frequencies $f < \text{day}^{-1}$. Hence, we still expect a good agreement with measurements on larger time scales.

Sensitivity of the SCM to the output time step of the simulations

For the extreme winds and the SCM, on the other hand, the higher energy on short time scales might be problematic since the SCM strongly depends on the tail of the spectrum due to the important second-order spectral moment m_2 weighting the spectrum with f^2 . Due to the high energy in the tail, the value of m_2 and consequently the SCM method and the resulting extreme wind estimates can be very sensitive to the output time step of the simulation, as illustrated in Figure 4. Choosing the output time step between 0.5 and 2 hours leads to an uncertainty caused by the time step choice in the order of 0.8 ms^{-1} for the annual average maximum and 2 ms^{-1} for u_{50} .

Figure 4: Estimated extreme winds using SCM depending on the output time step of the simulations for the location of FINO1. The gray circles show the estimates based on the original WRF time series, while for the black triangles a running 4-point average has been applied to the WRF data.

Usually, when undesired high-frequency dynamics are present in a signal, this energy is filtered out by a low pass filter, if possible before discretization. However, in our case we could not obtain a low-pass filtered output of the simulations, such as 10- or 30-min-averages but are bound to the saved data of the model which are instantaneous values every 30 minutes. Hence, we decided to apply a simple running two-point average (averaging two consecutive values) to this output corresponding to a filtering time scale of 60 minutes. The applied filter leads to a strong drop in the spectrum, as shown in Figure 3. For such a filtered spectrum, the integrals in equation are now well-defined since the spectrum approaches zero very fast. Consequently and most importantly, the SCM is now relatively insensitive to the choice of output time steps below 60 minutes. This insensitivity is hard to show for the two-point average since we only have data with an output time time step of 30 minutes. Thus, Figure 4 illustrates this phenomenon for a 4-point running average, reducing energy on time scales shorter than 2 hours.

Consequently, the extreme wind estimates are almost constant when applying the SCM to the filtered data showing that filtering the data can lead to a more consistent SCM procedure. In order to keep as much realistic low frequency information as possible but to remove enough non-physical high frequency energy, we apply the SCM to the WRF data filtered with the running two-point average. The filtered data will be simply referred to as the WRF data in the following.

Application of the SCM

We now apply the SCM method to the filtered WRF time series at the different measurement sites. As a first step, the PSDs of measurements and simulations are estimated at all sites (Figures 3 and 5). After correction, the spectra seem to match the measured ones relatively well for the offshore cases and the uniform terrain in Cabauw. It is remarkable that the diurnal peaks at $f = 1, 2, 3 \text{ day}^{-1}$ are matched really well for Cabauw.

In addition to the corrected spectrum using $f_c = 1.5 \text{ day}^{-1}$, the thin red lines in Figure 5 represent corrected spectra for $f_c = 1.2 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $f_c = 1.8 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Except for FINO3 these alternative corrected spectra do not differ strongly from the $f_c = 1.5 \text{ day}^{-1}$ case resulting in a small sensitivity of the SCM to f_c . For FINO3, a relatively high sensitivity to f_c is found since at $f_c = 1.2 \text{ day}^{-1}$ the slope of S still differs strongly from $-5/3$. This leads to an overestimation of the small-scale energy for $f_c = 1.2 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and consequently to a sensitive dependence of the correction factors on f_c for FINO3, as discussed further in the next paragraph.

Figure 5: Power Spectral Density of measurements and simulations for all measurement sites: (a) FINO1 (b) FINO2 (c) FINO3 (d) Cabauw. The thick red dashed line shows the corrected PSD for $f_c = 1.5 \text{ day}^{-1}$. In order to investigate the sensitivity on the value of f_c , all figures also include thin red dashed lines showing

the corrected PSD using $f_c = 1.2 \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $f_c = 1.8 \text{ day}^{-1}$. Since these lines are often really close to each other, they are not always easy to see indicating a low sensitivity to f_c .

The estimated extreme winds can be found in Table 2. Additionally, we compare the estimated correction factors with the actual ratios of the extreme winds for WRF and measurements in Table 3. For all three offshore sites the estimated annual average maxima are remarkably close to the measured ones indicating that the SCM seems to be able to take the smoothing effect successfully into account. For FINO1, for example, we find $\langle u_{max} \rangle = 27.6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ for the WRF simulations and SCM-corrected values of $\langle u_{max} \rangle = 30.0 \text{ ms}^{-1} \pm 0.7 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ close to the measured value $\langle u_{max} \rangle = 30.7 \text{ ms}^{-1} \pm 1.1 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The given uncertainty is one standard deviation of the sample mean. The correction factor is approximately $C = 1.09$ for all three offshore cases very close to the ratios of measurements and simulations (1.10, 1.08, 1.12). We estimate the uncertainty of the correction factor caused by the choice of f_c , which has been discussed above, to be around 0.004 for FINO1 and FINO2 and 0.008 for FINO3. This uncertainty needs to be investigated further and has to be kept in mind when using the SCM without measurements.

For the 50-year winds, the SCM also leads to values much closer to the measured ones than for the original WRF simulations (Table 2). However, in contrast to the annual average maxima, the 50-year winds are underestimated for all offshore sites but due to the high uncertainties, it is hard to assess if this is a significant result. One reason for a possible underestimation of the 50-year winds might be that the used WRF setup could have difficulties with the accurate modeling of storms. This will be examined further in the future. For the onshore site Cabauw, the SCM still leads to an improvement but it is not as good as in the offshore cases. Particularly, the 50-year wind seems to be strongly underestimated. The reason for this underestimation in the estimation and correction of the spectrum, since the corrected spectrum matches the measured one remarkably well. Former results in [5] show that combined with a microscale modeling approach, the SCM can yield a relatively good estimation at this site. Thus, the small-scale roughness and orography might play a more important role than we expected despite the simplicity of the site.

Annual average max. [ms^{-1}]	FINO1	FINO2	FINO3	Cabauw
WRF	27.8 ± 0.6	26.2 ± 0.6	27.4 ± 0.6	20.8 ± 0.4
WRF + SCM	30.0 ± 0.7	28.3 ± 0.7	29.6 ± 0.6	22.3 ± 0.4
Measurements	30.7 ± 1.1	28.4 ± 0.8	30.8 ± 1.0	24.4 ± 1.1
50-year wind [ms^{-1}]				
WRF	32.8 ± 2.3	31.6 ± 2.3	32.2 ± 2.2	24.3 ± 1.5
WRF + SCM	35.9 ± 2.5	34.8 ± 2.5	34.7 ± 2.3	26.1 ± 1.6
Measurements	39.3 ± 3.6	35.3 ± 3.0	38.5 ± 3.5	34.0 ± 3.9

Table 2: Extreme wind speeds: Estimates of average annual maxima and 50-year winds for measurements, WRF simulations and the corresponding corrected value. The statistical uncertainties are denoted as one standard deviation.

$\frac{1}{T}$	FINO1	FINO2	FINO3	Cabauw
WRF + SCM (Correction factor)	1.08	1.08	1.08	1.07
Annual average maxima (Measurements/WRF)	1.10	1.08	1.12	1.17
50-year wind (Measurements/WRF)	1.20	1.12	1.20	1.38

Table 3: Estimated correction factors and ratios of measured and simulated extreme winds.

3.4 Preliminary conclusions

The simulations set up for the New European Wind Atlas are based on the open source model WRF and the ERA5 reanalysis dataset. In this part of the report, we examined the combination of these simulations with the SCM, in order to estimate extreme winds.

A spectral comparison of the WRF simulations with the measurements indicates non-physical behavior of the simulations in the high-frequency region, a known phenomenon for mesoscale simulations with a relatively high spatial resolution. We illustrated that these high-frequency dynamics can be a significant source of uncertainty for the extreme wind estimation but that in the case of the NEWA data the application of a very simple low-pass filter leads to a robust estimation procedure.

Using the filtered WRF data, the SCM clearly improves the extreme wind estimates of the WRF simulation. Particularly offshore, estimates of the annual average maxima very close to the measured values have been found. The SCM also leads to valuable estimates of the 50-year wind but our results indicate a moderate systematic underestimation, which we will investigate further in Section 4.

For the onshore site Cabauw, the extreme wind estimates also lead to a clear improvement but still show a strong underestimation. It is likely that the small-scale orography and roughness plays a more significant role than expected. An even higher impact of these effects is expected at more complex sites, as investigated in Section 6. Thus, in a following step in Section 7, we will combine the SCM with a micro-scale modeling approach based on the WASP Engineering technique (see e.g. [6, 12]). This way the small-scale orography and roughness can be taken into account.

4. Interannual variability of the annual maxima

4.1 Introduction

Our results in Section 3 show that the application of the SCM to the NEWA simulations at offshore locations leads to accurate estimates of the average annual maxima. However, the 50-year winds might be systematically underestimated indicating a difficulty to capture the inter-annual variability of the annual maxima. In Section 3.2.2, we assume that the extreme winds u_T for all T as well as the average annual maxima $\langle u_{max} \rangle$ can be corrected by the same factor. In other words, we assume that through the smoothing effect of the simulations, the annual maxima u_{max} are simply multiplied by a factor smaller than one and can thus be corrected by a correction factor as estimated by the SCM. The result above questions this important assumption and will therefore be examined in greater detail in this section.

4.2 Results and discussion

A more detailed illustration of the findings discussed above can be found in Figure 6 showing the extreme winds u_T depending on T , as described by the formulas above. As expected, this relationship can be described by approximate straights in the semi-

logarithmic plot. For low T , the corrected extreme wind estimates $u_T^{WRF+SCM} = C \cdot u_t^{WRF}$ are pretty close to the estimates obtained from the measurements. This also confirms the accurate estimation of the average annual maximum, since it can be shown that $\langle u_{max} \rangle \approx u_{T=2.326 \text{ years}}$. For larger T , the different slope of the straight leads to an increasing deviation. Due to the large uncertainties of the estimates, however, it is difficult to draw conclusions on the significance of this result.

Assuming that $u_T^{Meas.}$ and $u_T^{WRF+SCM}$ are uncorrelated leads to large uncertainties of the ratio $\frac{u_T^{Meas.}}{u_T^{WRF+SCM}}$ (Figure 7) indicating insignificant differences of the ratios for different T . However, we expect $u_T^{Meas.}$ and $u_T^{WRF+SCM}$ to be strongly correlated since high extreme winds in the measurements should correspond to high extreme winds in the simulations. Under this assumption, the resulting lower uncertainty indicates a significant difference of the ratio. Due to $u_T^{WRF+SCM} = C \cdot u_t^{WRF}$, qualitatively similar results are found for $\frac{u_T^{Meas.}}{u_t^{WRF}}$ indicating that this ratio is not constant with T as it has been implicitly assumed in 3.2.2.

Figure 6: T -year extreme winds u_T versus T for the site FINO1. The error bars show the statistical standard error given by the AMM.

Figure 7: Ratio of extreme wind estimates from measurements and SCM procedure versus T for the site

FINO1. The standard errors assuming an uncorrelated and perfectly correlated extreme wind estimates are presented.

Simply assuming a multiplication of the annual maxima can also be expressed in terms of the Gumbel distribution. The Gumbel parameters β and α (slope of the approximate straight in Figure 6) should also differ by the same factor for simulations and measurements, i.e. $\beta^{(Meas.)} \approx C \cdot \beta^{(WRF)}$ and $\alpha^{(Meas.)} \approx C \cdot \alpha^{(WRF)}$. We find, however, $\frac{\alpha^{(Meas.)}}{\alpha^{(WRF)}} \approx 1.41 \pm 0.08$ and $\frac{\beta^{(Meas.)}}{\beta^{(WRF)}} \approx 1.09 \pm 0.01$. Hence, the change of β can be captured by the SCM while the strong change of α is underestimated. Note that this result directly corresponds to a strong change of the inter-annual variability since α is proportional to the standard deviation of the Gumbel distribution.

This raises the question, whether this strong change of the inter-annual variability can be a feature of the smoothing effect or whether the chosen WRF setup has some specific shortcomings such as the accurate modelling of storms. During the relatively long weekly runs, the mesoscale simulations could for example drift away from the driving reanalysis data. One way to investigate this question is to simply apply a filter to a measurement time series, in order to model the smoothing effect of the simulations. Hence, we apply a running average filter of approximately three hours to the measurement time series at FINO1 and apply the SCM method to this series, as if it was generated by a mesoscale simulation. As illustrated in Figure 8 this approach seems to yield qualitatively very similar results as the WRF simulations. This indicates, that the smoothing effect can be a possible reason for the stronger change of the inter-annual variability. Taking this change into account could potentially improve the estimation of extreme winds. However, this is a challenging task and the smoothing effect is not exactly modeled by a running average. It differs for every set of mesoscale simulations and the inter-annual variability might not be as strongly changed in other cases. Furthermore, as discussed, other sources than the smoothing effect for such a change are still possible.

Figure 8: T -year extreme winds u_T versus T for the site FINO1 obtained from the measurements and the application of the SCM to the filtered measurement time series. The error bars show the statistical standard error given by the AMM.

Figure 9: Ratio of extreme wind estimates u_T versus T for the site FINO1, obtained from measurements and the application of the SCM to the filtered measurement time series. The standard errors assuming an uncorrelated and *perfectly correlated* extreme wind estimates are presented.

4.2 Preliminary conclusions

Our results suggest that the smoothing effect of the mesoscale simulations can have a stronger impact on the inter-annual variability than on the average of the annual maxima. This leads to weaker estimations of the extreme winds u_T for higher T and particularly to a systematic underestimation of the desired 50-year wind in the order of approximately 4% to 10%. However, as discussed in Section 3, the SCM still strongly improves the extreme wind estimates of the simulations and leads to valuable estimates of the 50-year wind. Taking the stronger change of the inter-annual variability into account or choosing a WRF setup with a better representation of the inter-annual variability might lead to a further improvement of our approach but this beyond the scope of the project. It should therefore be investigated in future research.

5. Estimation of extreme winds at multiple kinds of sites (without downscaling)

For most sites, apart from offshore, the consideration of roughness and elevation effects is important – first, particularly the roughness values can be wrong, and, second, due to the low resolution of WRF there may be missing speed-up effects caused by roughness changes and small-scale orography. This, final estimates have to be interpreted with care as long as no specific downscaling is considered within the extreme wind estimation.

5.1 Results and discussion

[Here only a brief summary:]

- Results of correction factors and estimated extreme winds are shown in Figures 10 and 11.
- Even though other influences are important now, SCM leads mostly to an improvement of extreme wind estimates.
- However, e.g. for Karlsruhe the extreme winds are overestimated since the WRF simulations at this location already lead to an overestimation of extreme winds. The

- reason for this is an overestimation of energy in large scales, cf. Figure 12. This can e.g. be caused by an underestimation of the roughness for the forest around the site.
- Missing roughness and orography information can lead to an increase and decrease of the extreme wind estimates. Thus, it may make sense to consider it as a statistical source of uncertainty with a negligible bias in contrast to the smoothing effect which always leads to a decrease of the extreme wind estimates. Statistically it therefore still makes sense to apply the SCM on onshore sites even without a downscaling approach, although it may sometimes not improve the results.

Figure 10: Estimated ratio of extreme winds estimates of measurements and simulations (average annual maximum and 50-year wind) plus the estimated correction factors of the SCM. The error bars denote one standard deviation based on the statistical uncertainties of the AMM and assuming a linear correlation between WRF and Measurements. between Site Numbers: 1 FINO1 (100 m), 2 FINO2 (102 m), 3 FINO3 (90 m), 4 Cabauw (80 m), 5 Ijmuiden (85 m), 6 Lindenberg (98 m), 7 Hovsore (80 m), 8 Hamburg (110 m), 9 Karlsruhe (100 m), 10 Tystofte (39 m).

Figure 11: Estimated extreme winds of measurements and simulations before and after application of the SCM. Left: Annual average maximum, Right: 50-year wind. Site Numbers: 1 FINO1 (100 m), 2 FINO2 (102 m), 3 FINO3 (90 m), 4 Cabauw (80 m), 5 Ijmuiden (85 m), 6 Lindenberg (98 m), 7 Hovsore (80 m), 8 Hamburg (110 m), 9 Karlsruhe (100 m), 10 Tystofte (39 m).

Figure 12: PSD estimates and SCM correction for Karlsruhe.

6.2 Estimations at multiple heights

- The estimated correction factors are almost constant with height, see Figure 13 (for FINO1). Similar results are obtained for the other sites.
- The ratio of measurements and simulations indicate a slightly lower smoothing effect below 60 m. However, this can also be caused by a stronger influence of the sea surface roughness which is not perfectly modeled in WRF.

Figure 13: Ratios of extreme wind estimates of measurements and simulations and the corresponding SCM correction factors versus height at FINO1.

6.3 Preliminary conclusions

- Even though the uncertainty caused by the missing small-scale roughness and orography information can be even higher than the smoothing effect, we still expect the SCM to yield a systematic improvement to the extreme wind estimates.
- We recommend to offer an SCM corrected extreme wind estimate value (50-year wind) without downscaling for the complete atlas, in order to offer a first impression of the extreme wind climate.

[The downscaled extreme wind cannot be offered for the complete atlas since it would be computationally too expensive. However, alternatively we offer a generalized extreme wind climate everywhere. See Section 6.]

- It is probably enough to estimate the SCM factor only at one height and use it for correction at all heights.

6. Estimation of extreme winds with downscaling: a combination of SCM and WasP Engineering

As described in Section 2.1, the mesoscale simulations and thus also the used roughness and elevation fields have a resolution of approximately 3 km. Therefore, speed up effects caused by the small scale changes of surface roughness and orography may not be captured. In order to take these effects into account, we combine the SCM with a microscale modeling approach based on WASP Engineering. The combined procedure is introduced in the section but has not been applied yet due to missing input (WRF correction factors for generalization, which are to be derived from the final NEWA wind atlas simulations).

6.1 Methodology

Generalization of the WRF data

Before we apply WASP Engineering as a microscale modeling approach, we need to generalize the simulation data in order to avoid a double-counting of the effects caused by roughness changes and elevation. More precisely, we use the WASP-approach following e.g. [6], to estimate the wind speed in flat terrain with a uniform roughness of $z_{0,st} = 0.05$ m at a height of $z_{st} = 10$ m. In the first step the model LINCOS (DTU) is used to calculate correction factors s_0 , s_r for the speed-up effects due to orography and roughness changes. Additionally, LINCOS calculates an average roughness depending on the wind direction $z_0(\varphi)$, which is called upstream roughness in the following. The application of the correction factors

$$\tilde{u}(\varphi) = \frac{u}{(1+s_0)(1+s_r)}$$

yields a generalized wind speed corresponding to a homogeneous flat terrain with the constant roughness $z_0(\varphi)$. Assuming a logarithmic boundary layer profile we can now estimate the friction velocity

$$\tilde{u}^*(\varphi) = \frac{\kappa \tilde{u}(\varphi, z)}{\ln \frac{z}{z_0(\varphi)}}$$

and the geostrophic wind

$$G = G(\tilde{u}^*, z_0(\varphi)) = \frac{\tilde{u}^*}{\kappa} \sqrt{\left(\ln \frac{u^*}{f_{cor} z_0(\varphi)} \right) + B^2}$$

with the known parameters. We now apply the fundamental principle that the geostrophic wind stays the same before and after generalization.

Hence, after inserting $z_0 = 0.05$ m into the equation above we can solve for a new friction velocity $u_{st}^*(\varphi)$ and obtain the standard wind $u_{st}(\varphi)$ for the uniform roughness $z_{0,st} = 0.05$ m at the height of $z_{st} = 10$ m by again assuming a logarithmic profile. Details can be found e.g. in [6].

It should be noted that this generalization has to be performed for every grid point of interest and for all grid points when calculating the final wind atlas database. However, we only need to choose the wind speed time series from one height z , which we then generalize to $z_{st} = 10$ m. It should be investigated if our results are sensitive to this choice of z . (Sometimes it is e.g. suggested to use a height of around 50 m instead.)

Surface roughness over water

- The surface roughness over water is wind speed and thus time dependent. It is calculated in WRF using the Charnock Formula.
- Using the average roughness, which is used for the "normal" statistical downscaling might not work well for extreme winds since here a higher wind speed and thus roughness is important. (Instead the maximum roughness could be considered, which is currently recommended.)

Generalized extreme wind climates and SCM

Having obtained the standard wind from the WRF simulations for a specific site, we can apply the SCM, as it is described in Section 3.2.2, to the standard wind. This results in a correction factor C_{st} for taking the smoothing effect of the mesoscale simulations into account. WASP Engineering expects a generalized extreme wind climate (GEWC) as an input for its calculations consisting of the annual maxima $u_{max}(\phi)_{ij}$ and the corresponding wind direction ϕ for the number of years $i = 1..N$ and a number of wind direction sectors $(\phi_j - \Delta\phi, \phi_j + \Delta\phi)_{j=1..M}$. Here, we choose a number of $M = 12$ equidistant sectors. All found annual maxima are now multiplied by the correction factor C_{st} leading to a corrected GEWC which can now be used as an input to WASP Engineering.

Downscaling with WASP Engineering

In order to use WASP Engineering (WEng), the necessary small-scale information of a specific site needs to be provided. For this purpose, we download suitable surface roughness and elevation data. The considered regions are 40 km x 40 km large with the met masts in the approximate center. We choose a spatial resolution of 50 m for the microscale modelling ensuring an accurate calculation of shear and flow inclination in the domain. With this information the corrected GEWC can simply be imported into WEng and the 50-year wind on the met mast site can be estimated and compared with direct estimates from measurements.

Figure 14: Workflow for the combination of the SCM with a Downscaling based on WASP Engineering.

7. Conclusions and outlook

Our results suggest that the application of the SCM to the NEWA data leads to a promising correction of the smoothing effect and hence to reliable extreme wind estimates offshore. Furthermore, the combination with a downscaling approach enables us to apply this procedure also for onshore sites with significant microscale effects.

7.1 Setup for the final estimation procedure of extreme winds

The final estimation procedure composes the following steps:

- Filtering of WRF output with a two-point average
- Definition of numerical psd estimation procedure and spectral moment integration
- Choice of f_c and f_h
- Assumption of a Gaussian pdf and calculation of correction factor based on $\tilde{u}_{T0=1 \text{ year}}$
- WRF generalization setup incl. amongst others handling of sea surface roughness
- Recommendations for possible WEng setup

7.2 Wind atlas database

We plan to offer two different ways to present the extreme winds in the new European wind atlas. First, the "coarse extreme wind", as estimated in Section 3, will be given. Only the SCM is applied to the WRF data without any additional downscaling. Despite the resulting uncertainties onshore, this procedure still offers a good first impression of the extreme wind climate in Europe, particularly offshore. Additionally, we have to give a clear documentation (or even a flag in the atlas) that these estimates are unreliable for many sites.

Second, we are going to offer the SCM-corrected generalized extreme wind climate (GEWC) [5], which the user can use as an input to micro-scale modeling such as WASP Engineering. This way site-specific extreme wind estimates all over Europe can be obtained without having to perform a single measurement.

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